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Rethinking constitutionalism and democracy... again?

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Jan Komárek

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Abstract:

This is a review essay on three recently published books that seek to rethink constitutionalism and democracy in the context of European integration. The books are: Dieter Grimm, *The Constitution of European Democracy* (Oxford: OUP 2017), Athanasios Psygkas, *From the “Democratic Deficit” to a “Democratic Surplus”: Constructing Administrative Democracy in Europe* (Oxford: OUP 2017) and Turkuler Isiksel, *Europe’s Functional Constitution: A Theory of Constitutionalism beyond the State* (Oxford: OUP 2016). The review essay puts these books in the context of the Project IMAGINE and examines them as attempts to establish new constitutional imaginaries of Europe.

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KEYWORDS: European integration, European constitutionalism, constitutional ideology, utopia, imaginary

Jan Komárek is Professor of European Law, Faculty of Law, University of Copenhagen, and Principal Investigator of *IMAGINE: European Constitutional Imaginaries: Utopias, Ideologies and the Other* (<https://imagine.sites.ku.dk/>).

E-mail: Jan.Komarek@jur.ku.dk

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Rethinking constitutionalism and democracy... again?

Jan Komárek*

Dieter Grimm, *The Constitution of European Democracy* (Oxford: OUP 2017), x + 251 p., ISBN 978-0-19-880512-0

Athanasios Psygkas, *From the “Democratic Deficit” to a “Democratic Surplus”: Constructing Administrative Democracy in Europe* (Oxford: OUP 2017), xviii+351 p., ISBN 978-0-19-063276-2

Turkuler Isiksel, *Europe’s Functional Constitution: A Theory of Constitutionalism beyond the State* (Oxford: OUP 2016), xxvi + 265 p., ISBN 978-0-19-875907-2

Introduction

Each of the three recently published books that deal with constitutionalism and democracy in the European Union brings a different perspective on the same issue: the legitimacy crisis of European integration and its currently dominant form, the European Union. Dieter Grimm’s collection of essays translated from German is markedly a constitutional lawyer’s analysis of what he perceives to be the EU’s central problem: its ‘over-constitutionalization’. Athanasios Psygkas, as the subtitle suggests, focuses on the administrative side of the EU’s governance and seeks to extrapolate the argument to the EU as a whole. Finally, Turkuler Isiksel offers a new theory of ‘constitutionalism beyond the state’ and applies it to the EU, arguing that it has a specific type of constitution based on functionalist legitimation.

It is worth reading (and reviewing) the three books together, as each of them sheds light on the shortcomings of the other. As will be shown, Grimm’s analysis is firmly grounded in the state-based theory of constitutional democracy. It sees the lack of accountability as the main problem of democratic legitimacy and reconnecting the EU’s governance structures back to the Member States as the chief solution. This view is directly contradicted by Psygkas. Having chosen deliberative-participatory ideal of democracy as the starting point, he sees the EU as a structure that can in fact

* Professor of EU law, iCourts, Faculty of Law, University of Copenhagen. I would like to thank to Paul Linden Retek and Mike Wilkinson for their comments on an earlier version of this article. The article was written as part of the Project IMAGINE, which has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement No 803163).

improve democratic credentials of the Member States. Unfortunately, it does not offer answers to numerous concerns raised by Grimm, in particular the lack of social basis for establishing democracy at the EU level and the need for political contestation that goes beyond stakeholders' participation. Isiksel's books is the most innovative of the three and presents a genuine attempt to rethink the notion of legitimate constitutional authority anew. It provides a powerful (re-)construction of what the central commitments of constitutionalism might be, while remaining critical to the central object of inquiry. The question remains, however, whether Isiksel applies such standards correctly. If she did, this reviewer opines, the EU could not be considered as a case of 'constitutionalism beyond the state', but rather as evidence that it is hard to establish legitimate constitutional authority in structures that are different from the state.

I will take each book in turn and then conclude on a rather pessimist note.

Grimm: Is there no alternative to state-based constitutionalism?

Grimm's book collects articles published in various places and this at times harms the coherence of the whole collection: some chapters are more scholarly than others, which have been published as opinion pieces in outlets addressed to the general public.¹ There are several themes that run throughout the whole volume. Altogether they express Grimm's scepticism regarding the possible establishment of democratic constitutionalism at the EU level. The themes are the following:

- (a) The EU Member States are the basic units of democratic government; the EU and its institutions can never replace them; the EU's legitimacy depends on its Member States.
- (b) '[T]he real democracy problem of the EU lies in the autonomy of its executive and judicial institutions vis-à-vis its political institutions and the will of the Member States';² relatedly, the EU is 'over-constitutionalized' and the ECJ is the main culprit of this phenomenon;

¹ One may want to read another recently published collection by Dieter Grimm, *Constitutionalism: Past, Present, and Future* (Oxford: OUP 2016) in order to get a fuller grasp of Grimm's thinking on some of the issues addressed in the collection under review.

² Dieter Grimm, *The Constitution of European Democracy* (Oxford: OUP 2017), 12.

(c) The whole analysis is provided by a jurist. As Grimm himself declares, his ‘discipline is law, and law plays a predominant role in this book, both with respect to the diagnosis and with respect to the cure’.³

The continuous centrality of the nation state and its democratic constitution, which derives its legitimacy from popular sovereignty, is the founding stone of Grimm’s analysis. Very often Grimm compares the EU to its member states in order to show that the nation state is a far more advanced form of political organisation, which the EU cannot achieve (at least not in ‘the foreseeable future’).⁴ So in his view, the ‘European Union draws, as it always has, on the legitimation that emanates from the Members States, *which for their part are democratic*’.⁵ Grimm adds that ‘one might quarrel with one’s own state and execrate its current rulers, but *the state’s purpose and right to exist remain undisputed*’.⁶

But how solid is this founding stone?

Regarding the state of democracy in the Member States, Grimm is of course not blind to the problems that Western democracies are facing today (interestingly, half of the EU Member States in Central and Eastern Europe do not seem to be part of his story).⁷ Commenting on the problems of parliamentary democracy, Grimm notes: ‘In our highly individualized Western societies traditional ties of family, church, class, and milieu are unravelling, resulting in pluralism of values’,⁸ which makes it hard (according to Grimm) for parliaments to act as truly representative institutions for their societies.

This is a remarkably conservative rendering of the crisis of Western democracies. It does not include in the analysis the fact that parliaments today not only do not represent, but do not govern either. Representative democracy became ‘hollowed’ as the institutions that had mediated the relationship between the society and the state, especially political parties, have lost their significance and became

³ Ibid, viii.

⁴ References to the ‘foreseeable future’ are made at several places; Grimm therefore does not seem to exclude a deeper transformation of the EU conceptually, only as a matter of actual realization.

⁵ Ibid, vii, emphasis added.

⁶ Ibid, 2, emphasis added.

⁷ It is of course rather contentious today to say, without further elaboration, to what extent post-communist countries became democratic due to their membership in the EU. See Jan Komárek, ‘Waiting for the existential revolution in Europe’ (2014) 12 *International Journal of Constitutional Law* 190-212.

⁸ Ibid, 106.

empty shells.⁹ There is a ‘void’ between the society and the state, ‘a zone of disengagement’, since citizens have mostly withdrawn to their private spheres.¹⁰ The reason for this, contrary to the conservative story, is the cartelization of politics, whereby ‘political competition is increasingly oriented around the question of the efficient management of the state (“competence”) rather than rival ideological programmes’.¹¹ ‘Efficient’ means maintaining the current political and economic order, no matter how much injustice and suffering it produces. The EU’s response to the financial crisis and the distribution of costs (or suffering) confirms thus.¹² There (seems to be) no alternative to the regime of ‘authoritarian liberalism’.¹³ Grimm mentions that ‘most parliaments in democratic states see their significance dwindle’,¹⁴ but misses the ideological dimension of this phenomenon – the ‘void’.

Questions can be also raised at the conceptual level: it seems rather outdated to say that – *conceptually* speaking – Member States (which means for Grimm *nation* states) are for their part democratic, without at least considering externalities that territorially bounded democracies (no matter how perfect internally) impose one onto each other and also globally.¹⁵ It may be true that boundaries are *practically* necessary for democracies to be able to make decisions and externalities thus inevitable.¹⁶ It should however not exclude the possibility that democracy’s closure is in tension with its foundational ideals, such as that all affected are included. The EU on this view surely produces externalities in the global system; at the same time, however, it may be helping to address this problem at least among its Member States. In the light of the twentieth-century history of the European nation state it not an achievement that should be entirely overlooked by Grimm.

Objections can be also raised against the seemingly unquestionable ‘right to exist’ of the state, both at the practical and conceptual level. Regarding the former, it may be true that the big Member States and their nations that have existed (some of them in various forms, to be sure) for centuries have

⁹ Christopher Bickerton, ‘Beyond the European void? Reflections on Peter Mair’s legacy’ (2018) 24 *European Law Journal* 268-280.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 272.

¹¹ *Ibid.*, 274.

¹² See Armin Schäffer and Wolfgang Streeck (eds), *Politics in the Age of Austerity* (Cambridge: Polity Press 2013).

¹³ On this notion see particularly numerous works by Michael Wilkinson, most notably ‘Authoritarian Liberalism in the European Constitutional Imagination: Second Time as Farce?’ (2015) 21 *European Law Journal* 313-339.

¹⁴ Grimm, n 2, 107.

¹⁵ See e.g. Eva Erman, ‘The Boundary Problem and the Ideal of Democracy’ (2014) 21 *Constellations* 535-546.

¹⁶ Alexander Somek, ‘The Darling Dogma of Bourgeois Europeanists’ (2014) 20 *European Law Journal* 688-712, 699-700.

never raised questions regarding their right to exist and possibly their purpose. Most of the states that have been formed after the collapse of the Austrian-Hungarian Empire after the World War One have quite different experience, as quite drastically the book by the American historian Timothy Snyder's *Black Earth*¹⁷ documents. Since their establishment, these states had to justify their existence to the Great Powers and some of them employed quite sophisticated propaganda tools, as e.g. Andrea Orzoff's *The Battle for the Castle* shows on the example of the interwar Czechoslovakia.¹⁸ Czechoslovakia's founding figures successfully created the myth of the East-Central Europe's most devoted democracy, a myth which have survived until today and has motivated the country's 'return to Europe', from where it was apparently kidnapped by the Soviet Empire or the communists.¹⁹

The 'right to exist' might not be a matter of course for the big states either, however. This is true for not only Germany, which had to justify its semi-independent existence to the Allied Powers after World War Two, but other countries as well. As the title of a book by Alan Milward, *The European Rescue of the Nation-State*,²⁰ suggests, the continuous existence of European nation states has been dependent on establishing structures of economic and political cooperation that would later start to transform the nature of their statehood. This is well shown by another recent book on *European Integration: From Nation-States to Member States* by Chris J. Bickerton.²¹ In his analysis combining comparative politics, sociology and economy, European states became capable to govern their societies only through external structures and rules. The 'void' between the state and society, mentioned above, is covered by the EU and its byzantine governance structures, where national governments take part, but nobody really knows who holds the ultimate power to take decisions.

What sticks rather firmly with the people living in Europe, both in the West and East, is merely 'the fable of the wise nation', as the already-mentioned historian Timothy Snyder calls it. Snyder claims firmly:

In history there was no era of the nation-state: generally (with exceptions such as Finland), empire ended while integration began, with no interval in between. ... Europeans settled for a falsehood. The fable of the wise nation, learned in

¹⁷ Timothy Snyder, *Black Earth: The Holocaust as History and Warning* (London: Vintage Books 2016).

¹⁸ Andrea Orzoff, *Battle for the Castle: The Myth of Czechoslovakia in Europe, 1914-1948* (Oxford: OUP 2011).

¹⁹ See Komárek, n 7, 194.

²⁰ Alan Milward, *The European Rescue of the Nation-State* (Abingdon: Routledge, 2000).

²¹ OUP 2012.

childhood, comforted adults by allowing them to forget the true difficulties of history. By reciting the fable of the wise nation, leaders and societies could praise themselves for choosing Europe, when in fact Europe was an existential need after empire.²²

Bickerton's book links to another objection concerning the centrality of the nation state in Grimm's analysis, this time conceptual. Jens Bartelson opens his book *The Critique of the State*, published already in 2001, thus: 'Today there is a widespread conviction that the sovereign state is unlikely to remain the main source of political authority in the future'.²³ Since the advent of neoliberalism in the 1970s and the fall of 'communism' in 1989 the state as an idea and an institution is held in deep suspicion both in constitutional theory and practice – under many influences, and the economic liberalization and the ensuing rule of the markets over states (or capitalism over democracy, to put the matter more provocatively) is just one of them.²⁴

Grimm notes the 'neoliberal bias' in the EU constitution, relying in his analysis on Fritz Scharpf.²⁵ At the same time however, he sees it as a problem imposed on the Member States by the ECJ rather than as something at least co-created by national governments that were more than happy to accept the constraints coming from 'a clandestine loss of powers through the ECJ's expansive interpretation of the treaties'.²⁶ The fact that 'the Member States could not longer freely decide which areas to leave to the market and which to govern themselves',²⁷ was at least partially the choice accepted or even made by (some of) them.²⁸

This does not mean, however, that once this choice has been made, it can be easily undone. Member States can be the 'Masters of the Treaty', but this is true only in increasingly scarce moments: when they decide on future treaty amendments, and even this only to a certain extent. The example of Ireland and its repeated referendum on the Lisbon Treaty shows that some Member States do not have even this option.

²² Timothy Snyder, *The Road to Unfreedom: Russia, Europe, America* (New York: Tim Duggan Books 2018), 76-77. Snyder's book is worth reading just to learn the lessons to draw from this fable.

²³ CUP 2001, 1.

²⁴ See Desmond King and Patrick Le Galès (eds), *Reconfiguring European States in Crisis* (Oxford: OUP 2017).

²⁵ *Governing in Europe: Effective and Democratic?* (Oxford: OUP 1999).

²⁶ Grimm, n 2, 6.

²⁷ *Ibid.*

²⁸ This argument is made by Bickerton, n 21 and supported by e.g. Clemens Kaupa, *The pluralist character of the European economic constitution* (Oxford: Hart Publishing 2016).

This relates to Grimm's analysis of sovereignty in Europe, so much based on the German trope of the 'Masters of the Treaty' introduced to European constitutional discourse by the Federal Constitutional Court. Conceptually speaking, Grimm distinguishes between 'public power' and 'sovereignty'. While in his view the EU can exercise the former quite autonomously, the latter rests with the Member States only. Grimm uses, rather oddly, the term 'self-determination' to make his point: while the EU has a great deal of *self-determination* as regards its secondary law-making and law enforcement, it is not the kind of self-determination that would make the EU *sovereign*:

The type of self-determination, which is an expression of sovereignty, refers exactly to the existence and form of a political entity, i.e. to the constitutional level, in European terms *to the primary law*. Sovereign is an entity that has this power, whereas it seems difficult to call a political entity sovereign that cannot independently determine its existence, its purpose, its form, and its competencies.

This is the case with the EU. It lacks *the constituent power*.²⁹

Grimm rejects Habermas's idea of dual sovereignty, whereby the EU finds its constituent power in European citizens who can act in dual capacity as such and at the same time as the citizens of their Member States.³⁰ In Grimm's analysis, European citizens are not involved in treaty amendment process (Article 48 TEU) and therefore 'the constituent power of the EU remains in the hands of the Member States'.³¹ At another place Grimm adds: 'The legitimating principle of the treaties is not popular sovereignty, but rather state sovereignty'.³²

Many chapters of the book then build on this view: they discuss the importance of the nation-state-based institutions, such as constitutions, constitutional courts or national parliaments for the legitimacy of the EU. Nowhere in the volume has Grimm considered an opposite question: how important for the legitimacy and the very existence *of the present member states* the EU is.

The centrality of states should, according to Grimm, 'prevent the EU from constantly lowering the political substance of the Member States and the impact of their democratic structures and

²⁹ Grimm, n 2, 47, emphasis added.

³⁰ Jürgen Habermas, *The Crisis of the European Union: A Response* (Cambridge: Polity Press 2012).

³¹ Grimm, n 2, 51.

³² *Ibid*, 60.

processes'.³³ This is not to say that the EU's legitimacy depends on national institutions only. In Grimm's view, the EU's legitimacy stands on two pillars, one external, 'grounded in the democratically elected and accountable governments of the Member States', and the other internal, 'grounded in a European parliament elected by EU citizens'.³⁴ For Grimm, however,

the two pillars are not equally sturdy. The flow of legitimacy from the Member States is considerably stronger, in part because the Council wields more significant powers, in part because the conditions for a living (not merely a formal) democracy are much more promising in the Member States than in the EU.³⁵

The key problem of democratic legitimacy consists in a 'yawning gap between decision-making power and accountability'.³⁶ This claim relates to Grimm's suspicion of two (relatively) most autonomous institutions of the EU: the Commission and the ECJ, and especially the latter. In Grimm's view, '[i]ntegration was driven primarily by what, based on its functions, was the least likely European institution; the European Court of Justice'.³⁷ Based on its jurisprudence, the Treaties became 'over-constitutionalized', which in Grimm's view, is the central problem of the EU.

This is because in Grimm's view, 'constitutions regulate the production of political decisions, but they do not themselves make political decisions'.³⁸ The Treaties, with their list of objectives, with the creation of the Common (and later Internal) Market however do exactly that. Grimm notes: 'To be clear: the point is not to abandon constitutionalization, but to draw proper conclusions from the constitutionalization that has already taken place'.³⁹

There comes the weakest point of Grimm's analysis, which confirms that it was written by a jurist: his prescriptions. They are spread over most of the chapters, each focusing on a different aspect of the EU's legitimacy crisis.⁴⁰ Distilled from that, they should consist of the following:

³³ Ibid, 56.

³⁴ Ibid, 17.

³⁵ Ibid.

³⁶ Ibid, 12.

³⁷ Ibid, 3.

³⁸ Ibid, 31. For the sake of brevity, I will not entertain the 'liberal fallacy' contained in this view: all constitutions structure political decisions in a certain way and are not fully neutral. See Mark Warren, 'Liberal Constitutionalism as Ideology: Marx and Habermas' (1989) 17 *Political Theory* 511-534.

³⁹ Ibid, 35.

⁴⁰ They can be found, in particular, on the following pages: 18-19 and 35-37 (as related to legitimacy in general), 114-115 (as related to the role of the European Parliament and democracy in the EU), 123-129 (as related to European elections and parties).

- (a) '[T]o reclassify all provisions of a non-constitutional nature as ordinary law – basically the entire [TFEU]. Undesirable interpretations could then be corrected by legislation, as happens in every democratic state'.⁴¹
- (b) '[T]here must be a catalogue, based on subject matter, in which certain areas are reserved to the states – even if under certain conditions those areas affect the common market'.⁴²
- (c) '[T]here needs to be a discussion of ultimate goals', instead of the reassurances that such 'questions will be addressed when the time for decision arrives'.⁴³ Relatedly, 'decisions with significant political implications must be re-politicized'.⁴⁴

The first proposal is the most startling: Grimm's views of the political process in the EU are clearly informed by the analysis of the prevalence of the 'negative integration' over 'positive' one formulated by Fritz Scharpf.⁴⁵ Given the numerous structural (and ideological) constraints of the EU legislative process, so well analysed by Scharpf (and others),⁴⁶ it does not make much difference to put one's bet on the EU's legislator and hope that it will correct 'undesirable interpretations', if some TFEU provisions are downgraded to the 'sub-constitutional' status. For a 'pure jurist', it may appear easier to amend secondary legislation than to amend the Treaties; in reality both are quite cumbersome, although each for different reasons.⁴⁷

The second proposal seems equally antiquated: it was, after all, the hope of the Laeken Declaration to put a stop on the 'competence creep'⁴⁸ by providing for a 'better division and definition of competence in the European Union'.⁴⁹ As Sacha Garben has recently argued, however, such approach based on 'categorical federalism'⁵⁰ is fundamentally flawed. The main reason consists in the

⁴¹ Ibid, 18; see also 36.

⁴² Ibid; see also 35 and 114.

⁴³ Ibid, 19.

⁴⁴ Ibid, 35.

⁴⁵ *Governing in Europe: Effective and democratic?* (Oxford: OUP 1999), especially Chapter 2.

⁴⁶ See e.g. Martin Höpner and Armin Schäfer, 'Embeddedness and Regional Integration: Waiting for Polanyi in a Hayekian Setting' (2012) 66 *International Organization* 429-455.

⁴⁷ See Susanne K. Schmidt, *The European Court of Justice and the Policy Process: The Shadow of Case Law* (Oxford: OUP 2018). For a relatively more optimistic analysis see Dorte Sindbjerg Martinsen, *An Ever More Powerful Court? The Political Constraints of Legal Integration in the European Union* (Oxford: OUP 2015).

⁴⁸ See Stephen Weatherill, 'Competence Creep and Competence Control' (2004) 23 *Yearbook of European Law* 1-55.

⁴⁹ Ref____.

⁵⁰ Sacha Garben, 'Confronting the Competence Conundrum: Democratising the European Union through an Expansion of its Legislative Powers' (2015) 35 *Oxford Journal of Legal Studies* 55-89,

impossibility to categorize, or classify, unequivocally certain measures as falling within one or another domain. Grimm's analysis however appears as if no such debate existed.

The third proposal echoes a bold suggestion made some time ago by Mark Dawson and Floris de Witte.⁵¹ While they present a rather sophisticated formula on how to create conditions for such contestation over the EU's objectives to be productive, Grimm resorts to a rather empty formula: 'the Europeanization of the European elections and the creation of truly European parties that are in touch with society, campaign on the basis of European electoral platforms, and then feed the views on European policy and the interests of their electorate into the decision processes in Brussels'.⁵²

How to do this Grimm does not say, however. It is true that there is a huge disconnect between the national parties that run in European elections and the European parliamentary groups that actually direct the work of the Parliament. The real issue, however, is that in the EU's byzantine governance structure it is not clear how the result of the European elections can actually influence the policies of the EU. Insisting on the primary role of the Member States in creating the democratic legitimacy of the EU runs against this – but is never at least acknowledged by Grimm.

Psygkas: From telecommunications to democracy in all Europe?

One response to Grimm, recognizing the limitations that states and their democratic institutions face today, can be that the EU in fact helps to address them. By taking part in the EU's governance structure, the Member States become more democratic, not less. That is essentially the argument made by Athanasios Psygkas, *From the "Democratic Deficit" to a "Democratic Surplus"*.⁵³ It directly challenges Grimm's view about the lack of accountability in the EU and argues that 'the structure of the EU regulatory state may actually enhance certain aspects of the democratic accountability of national regulatory agencies at the member-state level through the creation of participatory channels for European stakeholders'.⁵⁴ It is based on a different model of democratic accountability than 'the classic representative variant'.⁵⁵ Instead it construes a 'deliberative-participatory model', which is elaborated in the first, theoretical chapter of the book. The following

⁵¹ 'From Balance to Conflict: A New Constitution for the EU' (2016) 22 *European Law Journal* 204-224.

⁵² *Ibid.*, 114 and in detail 123-129.

⁵³ Athanasios Psygkas, *From the "Democratic Deficit" to a "Democratic Surplus": Constructing Administrative Democracy in Europe* (Oxford: OUP 2017).

⁵⁴ *Ibid.*, 5.

⁵⁵ *Ibid.*

chapters explore how the model works in one concrete sector of EU policy: telecommunication services, which were thoroughly Europeanized – and liberalized – in the course of the 1990s and early 2000s. The books undertake a deep comparative study of this process in three EU Member States – France, the United Kingdom, and Greece.

Given the focus of this review article, I will focus on the theoretical chapter and the broader claim it makes about democratic legitimacy in the EU. According to Psygkas, there are three versions of democratic deficit in the EU: the first insists that ‘the adoption and implementation of EU policies should be legitimized through the democratically elected European Parliament’.⁵⁶ This in Psygkas’ view ‘overly relies on a model of legitimacy that is “uploaded” from national parliamentary systems onto the EU level. Hence, it ignores or underestimates other effects that EU law has on the national legal orders that might undercut the notion of the EU “democratic deficit”’.⁵⁷

The second version of democratic deficit most closely corresponds to Grimm’s analysis. According to this version, the EU’s democratic legitimacy derives from the Member States. Once they lost their veto power in the Council with the rise of qualified majority voting, their national parliaments lost control, as well, and the chain of legitimacy was broken. Psygkas finds three responses to this argument:

- (a) ‘The perception of the member states as the most important—albeit indirect—source of legitimacy is not sufficient to provide an “adequate normative foundation for its supranational component,” which as we saw becomes increasingly salient as integration proceeds’.⁵⁸

This in itself is hardly a reply, however. Grimm would most likely say that it is the excess of the supranational level, which needs to be contained by a better control by national institutions – governments in the Council, which are accountable to domestic parliaments.

⁵⁶ Ibid, 1.

⁵⁷ Ibid, 2.

⁵⁸ Ibid, 2, with reference to Giandomenico Majone, ‘Europe’s ‘Democratic Deficit’: The Question of Standards’ 4 (1998) *European Law Journal* 5, 12.

(b) ‘[T]he veto power itself might contribute ... to the democratic deficit since it allows only a few European citizens through their Minister in the Council to thwart the collective decisions of the rest of the Union.’⁵⁹

This is something which Grimm indeed does not consider at all: it is a view, however, which assumes that there exists some political community at the EU level – the community of EU citizens who come together in the EU. Such community would set up a framework of the EU for exercising *their political autonomy*, alongside the processes and institutions that are available at the level of the Member States. Psygkas however does not present any argument in that respect and simply assumes that there is a *political community* beyond the Member States.

(c) The third kind of response concerns the apparent neglect of the role of Member States institutions other than their ministers and parliaments, especially national regulatory authorities.

This response concerns the central argument of the book, and I will come back to it below.

The third version of the democratic deficit considered by Psygkas concerns ‘[t]he fear ... that while the policymaking capacity of member states is being weakened, the EU itself lags behind member states in social protection’.⁶⁰ In Psygkas view, this concern is not about ‘democratic *processes*’, but rather ‘a lack of *substantive policy* outcomes linked to a specific agenda’.⁶¹ It ‘denotes a failure of the institutional infrastructure to provide a framework of democratic contestation that would lead to the adoption of one or another substantive policy agenda’.⁶²

Psygkas sees this version of democratic deficit as essentially a version of the first, which both apply ‘standards derived from analogous national institutions or, more abstractly, from the majoritarian, “Westminster” model of democracy’.⁶³ The central quest of his book is to present an alternative model, based on Habermasian model of ‘deliberative-participatory democracy’. In Habermas’ own rendering, as conveyed by Psygkas,

⁵⁹ Psygkas, n 53, 2.

⁶⁰ Ibid, 3, with reference to

⁶¹ Ibid.

⁶² Ibid.

⁶³ Ibid.

civil society, which provides the social underpinning of autonomous publics, is as distinct from the economic system as it is from the public administration ... [T]he integrative force of solidarity ... should develop through widely expanded autonomous public spheres as well as through legally institutionalized procedures of democratic deliberation and decision making ... The public opinion which is worked up via democratic procedures into communicative power cannot itself “rule” but can only channel the use of administrative power in specific directions.⁶⁴

Psygkas distinguishes this account from others that may appear similar, and his main question is whether the model can be applied to the administrative state, and to the EU as such. Rather than replying in abstract, Psygkas identifies four elements that need to be fulfilled (open access, transparency, reason giving, and judicial review) and devotes the rest of the book to the comparative empirical study.

All in all, Psygkas book offers an interesting account of the legitimacy of the administrative state. To extrapolate that to the whole of the EU or to make an argument about democracy is a step too far, however. First, there is a general argument against the kind of democracy Psygkas presents as an ideal.⁶⁵ Deliberative democracy, especially if envisioned in the context of technocratic regulation, lies at the heart of the ‘void’ mentioned above.⁶⁶ It assumes that participation in the deliberative process is mostly about finding the ‘best’ solution, and not about contestation among groups that have different interests and also speak different political languages.

Second, and more importantly, his study concerns *regulatory policy*, where the legitimation stakes are much lower (such as various technical standards in the telecommunication sector) than it is where redistribution comes into play and becomes salient as a political issue.⁶⁷ It is hard to see how the same

⁶⁴ Jürgen Habermas, ‘Three Normative Models of Democracy’, in Ibid (Ciaran Cronin and Pablo De Greiff eds), *The Inclusion of the Other: Studies in Political Theory* (Cambridge: Polity Press 1998), 239-252, 249–50, as quoted in Psygkas, n 53, 6-7.

⁶⁵ See particularly Chantal Mouffe, *The Democratic Paradox* (London: Verso 2000) and also Mark Devenney, ‘The limits of communicative rationality and deliberative democracy’ (2009) 2 *Journal of Power* 137-154.

⁶⁶ See the text at n 9.

⁶⁷ See e.g. Scharpf, n 25, Chapter 3.

model can work in the post-crisis Europe, where even previously ‘technical’ and ‘expert’ issues (such as monetary politics) became politicized and contested.⁶⁸

Isiksel: As long as it works... but what?

The third book under review provides a very nice counter point to the preceding two. It openly challenges the central proposition of Grimm’s, arguing for ‘the necessity of directing political theory’s critical gaze towards new loci of political power, and of recalibrating its core concepts in order to do so’.⁶⁹ It offers a theory of constitutionalism beyond the state and applies it to the EU as a test case. It has a great deal to say about constitutionalism as such and deserves attention beyond the EU circles – which perfectly justifies its inclusion in the *Oxford Series in Constitutional Theory*.

At the same time, it does not limit democracy to transparency and accountability and asks difficult questions about the kind of politics the EU helps to sustain: ‘being associated in the public imagination with a common currency, commercial and capital mobility, market liberalization, and competition policy, its contribution to civic discourse has failed to move beyond a crude calculus of material affluence’.⁷⁰ It therefore touches on the question the conservative story offered by Grimm does not ask, and Psygkas technocratic account does not answer: the problem of the ‘void’ between the society and the government.

In order to formulate a novel account of constitutional authority, Isiksel applies a method of ‘reflexive readjustment’, whereby the concept of constitutionalism and the values it contains serve both as a conceptual grounding to assess (and potentially) criticize practices of constitutional government, while the same practices may lead to a readjustment of that very concept.⁷¹ Isiksel suggests that most discussions of constitutional authority still focus on two central principles: individual liberty and popular sovereignty.⁷² The EU has according to Isiksel produced ‘a qualitatively distinct form of constitutional practice’, which is functionalism, or one may say, effectiveness.

⁶⁸ See e.g. Fritz Scharpf, ‘Monetary Union, Fiscal Crisis and the Disabling of Democratic Accountability’ in Schäfer and Streeck (eds), n 12, 108-142. Politicization is of course in direct contradiction to deliberative democracy – see Philip Pettit, ‘Depoliticizing Democracy’ (2004) 17 *Ratio Juris* 52–65.

⁶⁹ Turkuler Isiksel, *Europe’s Functional Constitution: A Theory of Constitutionalism beyond the State* (Oxford: OUP 2016).

⁷⁰ *Ibid*, 18.

⁷¹ *Ibid*, 20 and 24-26.

⁷² *Ibid*, 5. This conceptual couple can be reformulated as the twin principles of individual and political autonomy.

Isiksel does not argue that this is something unique for the EU, as ‘effective government is a ubiquitous but underemphasized justification for constitutional mechanisms’ everywhere.⁷³ Isiksel thus presents a general *trilemma of constitutional authority*:

A constitutional system must be assessed not only in terms of how well it protects individual autonomy and allows for collective self-rule, but also in terms of how well it can realize those commitments *and* enable effective government.⁷⁴

Isiksel organises her argument around this trilemma, and puts it into effective use.⁷⁵ Being well-read both in political theory and political science, Isiksel connects various debates into a coherent notion of constitutional authority that can be applied to any government structure. It can explain why it is problematic to consider the nation state as being able to command constitutional authority without taking into account its practical limitations.

Some public law theorists may reply that this fails to distinguish between *potentia* and *potestas*: the practical power and legal authority of the government. Martin Loughlin thus argues that ‘in a conceptual sense, the authority of a government is unrelated to the power it is able to exercise’.⁷⁶ Those persuaded by Isiksel may respond that if authority is a legitimate power, then part of the legitimacy must be the effectiveness of that power.

In Isiksel’s view, the EU is unique in how this third principle of constitutional authority dominates over the other two, which remain relatively underdeveloped. Moreover, the EU’s functionalism focuses on just one goal: delivering a market, other objectives and competences notwithstanding. The following passage embodies the spirit and message of Isiksel’s book and deserves quoting at length:

While most observers tend to see the expansion of the EU’s tasks as evidence that it has grown beyond its economic origins, however, I contend that the reverse is true: the expansion of the EU’s operations has engendered the colonization of ever greater swathes of public policy by institutions designed primarily to create and govern a supranational market. ... The result is the refraction of key principles of political legitimacy such as democracy, equality, and solidarity, and of key

⁷³ Ibid, 8.

⁷⁴ Ibid, 9.

⁷⁵

⁷⁶ Martin Loughlin, ‘Constitutional pluralism: an oxymoron?’ (2014) 3 *Global Constitutionalism* 9-30, 12.

institutions such as representation, citizenship, and constitutionalism through the prism of economic union.⁷⁷

Isiksel quite admirably takes one policy area, that may be seen as embodying the Union that has gone ‘beyond the market’, after another, and shows that the functionalist logic of establishing the market lies at their heart: there is market fundamentalism behind the regime of EU fundamental rights; the most effective means of agency in decision-making processes ‘are configured to advance the substantive commitments to market integration’;⁷⁸ EU citizenship is one of aliens ‘that protects and empowers those who move, but remains mostly inert for those who stay’;⁷⁹ and finally, ‘[b]y extrapolating market-based rules against discriminatory treatment to govern other, more complex human relations, the EU has opted for a weak, voluntarist, and negative norm of equality over richer conceptions of social inclusion that might include reciprocity, stronger social assistance, and fair equality of opportunity’.⁸⁰

The final chapter is thus entitled ‘Waking from the European Dream’ and discusses the limitations of the EU functionalism in the light of the Euro-crisis and the EU’s response to it. Herein lies the central ambiguity of the book: on the one hand Isiksel wants to argue that there may be new forms of constitutional government beyond the state and that the EU may embody one. To pursue this argument Isiksel comes up with her ‘conceptual readjustment’ of the core notions behind constitutional authority and adds ‘functionalism’ as a third one.

If all three need to be satisfied at the same time – but at the same time they cannot (hence the trilemma), then the EU clearly does not pass the test – and that may suggest that in fact it is not possible to apply the idea of constitutionalism to other forms of political ordering than the state. The question, with which Isiksel opens the book, may then lead to a different answer than that offered by Isiksel.

The need to re-imagine

In Grimm’s view, the European democratic deficit ‘does not ... consist in following a model other than the nation-state model, but rather in the development of autonomous areas reached neither by

⁷⁷ Ibid, 19.

⁷⁸ Ibid, 130.

⁷⁹ Ibid, 158.

⁸⁰ Ibid, 188.

national nor by European legitimacy'.⁸¹ Grimm complains that 'most proposals for repairing the EU's legitimacy deficit, however, embrace the nation-state model'.⁸² In my view, however, he commits the same error. Sure, he does not want the EU to become a state; at the same time, however, his conceptual imagination is limited to that of the nation state or categories developed at the time when the state could indeed be the "master noun" of modern political argument'.⁸³

Neither Psygkas nor Isiksel come with persuasive alternatives, although particularly the latter's conceptual framework should indeed interest those, like Grimm, who put their bet on the continuing (and unquestionable) relevance of the nation state. We therefore end with Martin Loughlin's observation: it may be true

that this claim about the state is founded on a set of modern factors which no longer pertain and that, just as that scheme of intelligibility was able to draw its imaginative power from the emergence of a modern system of nation states, then so too can we devise a new juridical scheme drawing on contemporary post-modern conditions. This may indeed be the case. The difficulty is that no one has yet managed to sketch an alternative to match the sophistication and sheer imaginative power of the modern state-founded discourse.⁸⁴

Indeed – but especially Isiksel's book is a step in the right direction.

⁸¹ Grimm, n 2, 77.

⁸² Ibid, 78.

⁸³ Martin Loughlin, *Foundations of Public Law* (Oxford: OUP 2010), 183, referring to Quentin Skinner, *The Foundations of Modern Political Thought*, Vol. II (Cambridge: CUP 1978), 358, 349.

⁸⁴ Martin Loughlin, 'The state: *Conditio sine qua non*' (2018) 16 *International Journal of Constitutional Law* 1156–1163, 1163.

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Jan Komárek is Professor of European Law, Faculty of Law, University of Copenhagen, and Principal Investigator of *IMAGINE: European Constitutional Imaginaries: Utopias, Ideologies and the Other* (<https://imagine.sites.ku.dk/>).

E-mail: Jan.Komarek@jur.ku.dk

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- The Danish National Research Foundation's Centre of Excellence for International Courts
The Faculty of Law

University of Copenhagen

Karen Blixens Plads 16

2300 Copenhagen S

E-mail: icourts@jur.ku.dk

Tel. +45 35 32 26 26